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**CAIRT mission test data set product descriptions for
impact study on Age of Air**

README-1

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This document describes the simulated CAIRT L2 profiles of ozone used as test dataset-product (TDS-P) used in the study measuring the impact of CAIRT L2 profiles of long-lived species (CFC-11, CFC-12, CH₄, HCFC-22, N₂O and SF₆) on age-of-air retrieval.</p>		
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List of acronyms

ACT	ACross Track
ALT	ALong Track
AoA	Age of Air
AK	Averaging Kernel
BDC	Brewer Dobson Circulation
BASCOE	Belgian Assimilation System for Chemical Observations
CAIRT	Changing Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography explorer
CLaMS	Chemical Lagrangian Model of the Stratosphere
CTM	Chemistry Transport Model
EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
FL2S	Fast Level 2 Simulator
LPE	Linear Performance Estimation
MAO	Model At Observation
MLS	Microwave Limb Souder
MLT	Mesosphere Lower Thermosphere
MO	Mission Objective of CAIRT
NR	Nature Run
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction system
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
PerReC	CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study
SciReC	CAIRT Scientific and Requirement Consolidation study
SO	Scientific Objective of CAIRT
TDS-P	Test Data Set-Product
UTLS	Upper Troposphere Lower Stratosphere
WP	Work Package (of PerReC if no other project mentioned)

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide a description of the test data set product (TDS-P) produced for the CAIRT impact study about Age of Air (AoA). Here, TDS-P are simulated CAIRT L2 profiles of six long-lived species (CFC-11, CFC-12, CH₄, HCFC-22, N₂O and SF₆) produced following this chain of processes:

1. Run a model Nature Run (NR) providing reference atmosphere for the six long-lived species
2. Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid, leading to NR@CAIRT
3. Simulate CAIRT L2 profiles given NR@CAIRT, the Fast Level 2 Simulator (FL2S) and the Linear Performance Estimation (LPE) files of CAIRT
4. Produced CAIRT superobservation files for BASCOE-EnKF, as justified in DEL-14-4.

These steps are defined in Sect. 2. The file format of CAIRT L2 and superobservation NetCDF files are described in Sect. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The codes and configuration files used to produce these files are stored on the BIRA-IASB subversion system or the FZJ git repository as detailed in the different subsections of this document and in Sect. 3.

2 Simulating CAIRT L2 profiles

2.1 The Nature Run (NR)

The nature run used in this study has been realized with Chemical Lagrangian Model of the Stratosphere (CLaMS) and is described in Voet et al. (2024) from which the information below has been extracted.

CLaMS is an offline lagrangian chemical transport model, usually driven by wind data from meteorological reanalysis (McKenna et al., 2002b, 2002a). The lagrangian formulation of transport sets CLaMS apart from most other chemical transport models that operate in an Eulerian framework. As such, CLaMS evaluates the mixing ratios of trace gases species along air parcel trajectories rather than on a fixed spatial grid. The number and distribution of these air parcels change with every time step, forming an adaptive irregular model grid.

The transport in the CLaMS model is based on a hybrid vertical coordinate, ζ , which changes from an orography-following coordinate in the lower troposphere to an isentropic, potential temperature coordinate above the tropopause region and throughout the stratosphere (for details see (Pommrich et al., 2014)). The model atmosphere is divided by ζ into 45 different layers. The lowest model layer (lower boundary layer of the model) extends from the surface to approximately 1.5 km (more precisely $0 \text{ K} < \zeta < 70 \text{ K}$). The uppermost model layer (upper boundary layer) covers the potential temperature range 2350 – 2650 K (altitude of about 55 km), hence the model domain extends from the surface to about the stratopause. The emissions of a trace gas over the course of the simulation are specified through its lower boundary condition as mixing ratios. In this study, the lower boundary condition of each trace gas is defined by a set of observation-based time series of zonal mean surface mixing ratios at different latitudes over the simulation period. The values of these time series are interpolated latitude-wise onto the lagrangian air parcels inside the lower boundary layer at the beginning of each new simulation time step. The air parcels in the upper boundary layer are treated in the same way, with an upper boundary condition on trace gas mixing ratios prescribed in the uppermost model layer. The influence of the upper boundary condition strongly depends on the properties of the given trace gas species in question. Six suitable trace gas species with long stratospheric life times and sources exclusively in the troposphere were selected for the study. These species are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of trace gases simulated by CLaMS in this study and the datasets used to create lower boundary conditions.

trace gas	datasets used to create lower boundary
Sulfur Hexafluoride (SF ₆)	(Dutton et al., 2022a)
Trichlorofluoromethane (CCl ₃ F), short: CFC-11	(Dutton et al., 2022c)
Dichlorodifluoromethane (CCl ₂ F ₂), short: CFC-12	(Dutton et al., 2022d)
Chlorodifluoromethane (CHClF ₂), short: HCFC-22	(Montzka et al., 2015)
Methane (CH ₄)	(Lan et al., 2023)
Nitrous Oxide (N ₂ O)	(Dutton et al., 2022b)

The tropospheric sources of these trace gases are represented by the lower boundary conditions, since none of them are products of chemical reactions in the atmosphere to any significant amount. The observation data sets used to create the lower boundary condition of each trace gas are referenced in Table 1: List of trace gases simulated by CLaMS in this study and the datasets used to create lower boundary conditions. The atmospheric losses of N₂O, CH₄, CFC-11 and CFC-12 are taken into account as described by (Pommrich et al., 2014). For the use in the present study, the additional trace gas species Sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) and HCFC-22 have been implemented into the CLaMS model. The depletion mechanisms for HCFC-22 implemented in CLaMS is represented by the reactions

The photolysis rates for the last reaction are calculated with the CLaMS photolysis code (Becker et al., 2000; Burkholder et al., 2019) for wavelengths ≤ 220 nm. Together, these three loss reactions form a significant sink in the stratosphere.

Sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) is the only trace gas in the list that does not have any significant chemical or photolytic loss reaction throughout the troposphere and stratosphere. SF₆ is mainly removed from the atmosphere through electron attachment in the mesosphere, outside the model domain. Therefore, SF₆ is treated simply as an inert tracer. However, depleted SF₆ mixing ratios transported downward from the mesosphere into the stratosphere are accounted for by the specification of a realistic upper boundary condition, which is based on measurements from the Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS). From these measurements, monthly zonal mean time series of SF₆ mixing ratios over the course of the measurement period were created at different latitudes for the potential temperature level 2500 K (Voet et al., 2024).

The time series at high latitudes shows strong seasonal cycles caused by the downward transport of SF₆ – depleted air from the mesosphere and the seasonality of the BDC itself. This set of time series is used as the upper boundary for SF₆ when the simulation time is within the time period of the measurements. The upper boundary condition for times outside of the measurement period was created by parameterizing the depicted seasonal cycle of each latitude with a sinusoidal least square fit and adding it to a shifted tropospheric tropical time series (taken from the lower boundary of SF₆). The time shifts correspond to the zonal mean age of air values at the respective latitude at the 2500 K potential temperature level. These mean age of air values were derived consistently from MIPAS measurements of SF₆ (Stiller, 2021).

Similar to (Pommrich et al., 2014), the N₂O and CH₄ climatologies of the Halogen Occultation Experiment (Grooß and Russell, 2005) were used as the respective upper boundary for these species in this study. CFC-11 and CFC-12 are decomposed completely well below about 2500 K and don't reach the upper boundary layer to any significant amount. Therefore, their upper boundaries were kept at zero throughout the entire simulation period. HCFC-22 does reach the upper boundary layer, but in relation to its tropospheric value

in much smaller quantities than SF₆. Mesospheric loss processes for HCFC-22 can therefore be neglected compared to the stratospheric ones (reactions R1 to R3). An open upper boundary condition has therefore been defined for HCFC-22. In addition to the six actual trace gases, a completely passive tracer without any atmospheric sources or sinks and linearly increasing lower boundary values was included into the model as well. It will be called the "clock-tracer" in the following and it will be used to calculate the "exact" mean age of air in the model using the standard lag time method described by (Hall and Plumb, 1994).

The simulation was driven with meteorological data from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis v5 (ERA5) reanalysis and covered the period from January 1, 1979, to December 31, 2022. For the initial condition of the simulated atmosphere, approximately 1.4 million air parcels were spread out by employing the principle of distributing air parcels based on entropy and static stability, as outlined by (Konopka et al., 2012; Pommrich et al., 2014). The mixing ratios of the six trace gases inside the initial air parcels were set to zero at the first time that is January 1, 1979. Thereafter, a 20 year long spin-up simulation has been carried out with repeating lower and upper boundary conditions and meteorology from the first simulation year 1979. This spin-up guarantees that the initial mixing ratio distributions of CFC-11, CFC-12 and the clock tracer at the first day of the transient simulation on 1 January 1979 represent the actual atmospheric conditions reasonably well.

The initial mixing ratio distributions of SF₆, CH₄, N₂O and HCFC-22 were estimated in a different way. The mixing ratios of these four trace gases in every air parcel on 1 January 1979 were all taken from mean tropical time series that were created from the respective lower boundary conditions. The points in time at which the mixing ratios were taken correspond to estimations of the points in time each air parcel was in contact with the surface for the last time before being transported to its final position on 1 January 1979. The estimations are based on annually averaged AoA values derived from observations of SF₆ by MIPAS (Stiller, 2021).

Simulation output for the year 2011, which is near the end of the operational period of MIPAS, was chosen for the analysis of the modeled satellite measurements. At the end of the operational period of MIPAS, the measurement-based upper boundary values of SF₆ had the maximal amount of time to spread below the upper boundary in the model atmosphere. The model output of SF₆, which is of particular importance for the aforementioned analysis, is therefore most representative of the real SF₆ distribution in the atmosphere for the year 2011. For the application of the proposed method on the GLORIA-B measurements, the CLaMS model output for the days of the two balloon launches was used. The version of CLaMS used in this study is similar to the one described by (Konopka et al., 2022) with the CAPE (convective available potential energy) triggering the unresolved convection in the model instead of the moist Brunt–Vaisala frequency. Both parameters as well as the convection parameterization are described in (Konopka et al., 2019).

2.2 *Regridding the nature run onto the CAIRT retrieval grid (NR@CAIRT)*

CLaMS model output has been interpolated onto the CAIRT retrieval grid using a trajectory mapping technique. For that reason, forward and backward trajectories have been started at each measurement point along the tracks and calculated to their positions at the next synoptic CLaMS model output time (12 UT every day). Thereafter, the model output has been spatially interpolated from the irregular Lagrangian air parcel grid onto the synoptic position of the measurement tracks.

The file format of the NR@CAIRT files produced at FZJ are not compatible by those read in BASCOE, which is using the NetCDF Observation file format for BASCOE (NOB, described in the SWB ATDB, see Höpfner et al., 2025). In particular, the order of dimensions for species profiles (time, track, altitude) used at FZJ and in

sim_CAIRT_grid.py differs from the order used at BIRA-IASB (time, lev, track) due to BASCOE constrain. The convention of variable names are slightly differing. A simple python CLaMS2NOB.py script has been written and applied to each daily NR@CAIRT for the necessary changes. It works with the following command:

```
> ./CLaMS2NOB.py YYYYmmdd
```

Where YYYY=year, mm=month and dd=day. Path to the input file and to the output file are defined in the script (see Sect. 3 for version number and versioning information). In the later part of this document, NR@CAIRT file preprocessed here are labelled NR_BIRA@CAIRT.

2.3 Perturbing NR@CAIRT using LPE and FL2S and production of CAIRT L2 NetCDF files

The daily files of NR interpolated onto the CAIRT retrieval grid (i.e. NR_BIRA@CAIRT) are perturbed and smoothed according to CAIRT errors from Linear Performance Estimation (LPEv3) files, done using FL2S (available at https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/cairt-scirec/cairt_fl2s and described in the CAIRT PerREC DEL-04-SWB ATBD) and the config file config_CAIRT_PhA_IS10.py. LPEv3 files are shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** TDS-P product files are in the NetCDF Observation file format for BASCOE (NOB), described in the SWB ATBD.

FL2S take as input daily NR_BIRA@CAIRT file. The command used to simulate daily CAIRT NOB files is the following:

```
> ./fl2s_run.py -Oaf full_path_to_input_NR_BIRA@CAIRT_file.nc -o output_filename.nc
config_CAIRT_PhA_IS10.py
```

The output NOB file format is described in the SWB ATBD and the config file is given Sect. 3.

2.4 Super observations

Due to the CAIRT spatial resolution, the number of CAIRT profiles are much larger than current limb instrument like MLS.

Method and codes for making super observations using mk_superobs.py are described in SWB ATBD and is used without change here. The superobservation file format (NOB) is described in the SWB ATBD and version information of the script mk_superobs.py is described in Sect. 3.

3 Versions, traceability and reproducibility

The codes and configuration files used to produce this TDS-P are either on the BIRA-IASB subversion system or on the FZJ CAIRT git repository. In the first case, all codes are below the following directory: <https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON>, in the second case, all codes are in jugit.fz-juelich.de:cairt-scirec. Code names, their corresponding processes, their location in the subversion/git system and their revision numbers are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Code names, their corresponding processes, their location in the subversion/git system and their revision numbers. All codes are available under <https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON>.

Code/config name	Process	Code location (svn means on the BIRA-IASB subversion system; git mean on the FZJ git repository; git_dkrz means repository on the gitlab.dkrz.de)	version of revision number
CLaMS model version	Production of NR	(git_dkrz) gitlab.dkrz.de/MESSy/MESSy.git	16b975df
config file of CLaMS simulation	Production of NR	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14264704	
sim_CAIRT_grid.py	Regridding of NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14264704	

CLaMS2NOB.py	Converting NR@CAIRT to NR_BIRA@CAIRT	(svn) stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS10/2_CLaMS2NOB	r13252
fl2s_run.py	simulation of CAIRT L2 profiles	(git) cairt_fl2s/main	r252e3a3e
config_CAIRT-PhA-IS10.py	simulation of CAIRT L2 profiles	(svn) stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS10/3_simL2	13145
mk_superobs.py	Creating superobservation file given L2 file	(git) cairt_superobs/main	r532d0000

Content of config_CAIRT-PhA-IS10.py:

```

para2ref = {'c2h6': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'hcooh': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'pan': '_mrd_thres_ref_2',
            'o3': '_mrd_thres_ref_2',
            'co': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'nh3': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'so2': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'h2o': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'h2so4-liq': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'temperature': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'ch4': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'n2o': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'cfc11': '_mrd_thres_ref_2',
            'cfc12': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'hcfc22': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
            'sf6': '_mrd_thres_ref_3'
}

lpe_ncdir = "/home/quentin/CAIRT/FL2S/lpe_v3_mrd_thres/ncfiles/"

CSSn = 'IS40'

mod_ncdir = "/home/quentin/CAIRT/data_t2/CSS/CSS7-SHW/css7shw2"

# define fl2s parameters
sol_activity = 0 # solar activity index (within 0 for low activity and 1 for high activity). The default is 0.
n_cal = 56 # calibration period length (in terms of acquisitions). The default is 100.
akd_threshold = 0.003 # averaging kernel threshold. The default is 0.003.
ak_noise_sys = {
    'ak': {'noi': False, 'sys': False},
    'aknoi': {'noi': True, 'sys': False},
    'aksys': {'noi': False, 'sys': True},
    'aknoisys': {'noi': True, 'sys': True},
}

# define across-track bins for different across-track averaging lengths of the lpe
act_bin_ind = {
    100: [[2,6],[6,10],[10,14],[14,18]],
    300: [[2,14],[2,14],[6,18],[6,18]],
}

```

```
# random generator seed method
# - auto: fixed seed based on date and target name + `random_seed` (below)
# - fixed: uses `random_seed` for all targets and dates
# - random (or anything else): no specific seed used, gives non-reproducible results
random_seed_method = "auto"

# fixed random seed or extra "jitter" for "auto"
#random_seed = 69063586
random_seed = np.random.randint(123456789)

# for faster test set to positive number to calculate only nmod_use samples along the tracks;
nmod_use = -20

css_config = {
  'IS10': dict(
  }

# Cloud mask information
cld_fraction_lim = 0.2 # Mask will be set for cloud fraction above cld_fraction_lim (if "cc" in model input
scenario file)
#cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-16_0.003.dat"
#cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-21_0.003.dat"
cld_impact_file = "/bira-iasb/projects/CAIRT/git_julich/cairt_fl2s/cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat" # The
most stringent case

# Path to temporary directory
scratch="/bira-iasb/scratch/quentin/CAIRT/tmp/"
```

4 Literature

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